

Bibliometric analysis and critical review of the research on the impact of Digitalization on Employment

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ABSTRACT: The fast moving emergent field of research addressing digitalization and its effect on employment is multifaceted, unstructured and plugged. Subsequently, both theoretical and practical research practice lack a rigorous foundation of prior available research to underpin and direct future exploration into the opportunities and challenges delivered by the digital technologies. Digital technologies do not merely affect the capacity and volume of jobs, they also transform the way that work is conceptualized and how people do their jobs. The purpose of the study is to review the articles to identify the trends, determine the current status of the research in the domain of Digitalization and Employment. This study employed a bibliometric analysis to explore extant published research within the digitalization and Employment domain.

Digital technologies are shown to perform a vital role in developing a resource-efficient industrial base in the labor market. The effective adoption of digital technologies can help reduce costs and improve the sustainability and flexibility of manufacturing industries. However, how digital technologies favor the transition towards manufacturing systems has not been analyzed in detail yet, so more conceptual and empirical investigation is required in this field. This study investigates the digital transformation trend in the manufacturing industry by combining the bibliometric method and literature mining. An integrated data analysis system (IDAS) is developed, which includes data collection, data analysis, and visualization processes. In this research, a bibliometric analysis, examines a sample of 7563 journal articles from the Scopus database from 1992 to 2022, using citation, co-citation, keyword clustering, critical review, and qualitative-bibliometric techniques. Further emerging research streams were evaluated using VOSviewer software

This paper aims to understand the knowledge progression and its present status, draw a thematic map, and identify future research directions. The results of this study may provide guidelines and reference points for the researchers, policy makers, industry professionals, job seekers, to study the progress of digitalization and its effects on employment in the Industries.

Keywords: Digitalization, Industries, Employment, Bibliometric, VOSviewer

[Introduction](#)

[Literature Review](#)

[Research Methodology](#)

[Bibliometric Results and Discussion](#)

[Limitation and Future Research Direction](#)

[Conclusion](#)

[References](#)

1. Introduction

The process of digitization is the way to convert the operations of the firm from manual to automatic. It means the industries are now capable of performing their business

activities by technologies. The digital technologies like smart phones, online socializing and communication system, cloud computing, social media and others have completely transformed the traditional working system of the industries. (Fossen, 2018). The employment impact of digitalization can have different dimensions. From an employment-level perspective, job loss related to automation when machines replace human input is widely discussed. At the same time, job creation is triggered by the emergence of new occupational profiles tailored to the exploitation of the new technologies, as well as by increasing demand for technology-based products and services due to lower prices or new markets, client groups or areas of demand. There can be substantial variations in terms of whether job loss or job creation dominates, whether numerical employment developments affect the same countries, regions, sectors, occupations and demographic groups, and whether they take place in parallel or at different points in time, depending on the technologies, their operational deployment in the economy and public policies.

Digitalization has postured new opportunities and challenges in the labor market both in Manufacturing and Service Industries. Digitalization is facilitating non-traditional forms of employment which provide greater flexibility and new patterns of employment. On the other hand, employment relationships have become increasingly blurred. This has posed significant challenges that are based on formal employment relations and changes in employees' skill composition.

Digitalization also promotes new forms of work, bring changes to employees' skill sets, job quality, it is facilitating non-traditional forms of employment which provide greater flexibility. New patterns of employment such as ICT-based mobile work and digitally-enabled forms of self-employment are gaining traction around the world. Non-traditional forms of employment, or non-standard employment, refer to the forms of work that 'falls out of the realm of the full time, indefinite work and as part of a subordinate and bilateral employment relationship'

The major impact of digital technology has occurred in the employment of the companies. This is one of the detailed functions of any organization due to multiple steps and measurements. However, the use of the digital system has created ease in the management process. Different studies shown that human capabilities and skills of the organization have enhanced after the revolution of organization operations into the digital system. Now, the organizations prefer to hire people with the knowledge of the digital system and advanced technologies (Fitzgerald, Kruschwitz, Bonnet and Welch, 2014).

Therefore, it is important to find the consequences of digitization over the employment of the companies. The employee, as well as organization, will be assessed to analyze how the digitization has transformed the strategies and approaches of the industrial sectors related to employment. This study aims to highlight those researches which dealt with the prospective changes in job losses, created and modified employment due to the new technologies, and tries to constitute a framework for further analysis to be made by researchers. The focus of this study is how companies and specifically manufacturing industries experiment with nature of new Business process and changes of employment as a result of digitalization

2. Literature Review

Most of the recent studies on the effects of automation on employment were primarily concerned with macro effects of digitalization on labor markets. Frey and Osborne (2017) have estimated that around 47 percent of the US labor force will face a high risk of automation of their jobs. Several follow-up studies for other countries could at least partly confirm that a significant share of jobs will face such a risk. For instance, Bode et al. (2017) provide very similar estimates for selected G20 countries, while their focus is on gender differences in the susceptibility of jobs to automation. Arntz et al. (2016, 2017) arrive at a less pessimistic scenario by emphasizing the within-occupational heterogeneity of tasks. Acemoglu and Restrepo (2017) show that deployment of industrial robots during the time period from 1990 to 2007 reduced the employment to population ratio and wages on the US labor markets.

Aleem et al. (2023), considering the effects generated by the COVID-19 pandemic, identified eight research themes: effect on employees at a personal level; effect on employees' careers; family life and gender roles; health, wellbeing, and safety; labor market dynamics; economic implications; remote work management; organizational remote work strategies. Cultural aspects can constitute factors of resistance to the adoption of remote work (Schulz et al., 2023) that's influenced by digitalization.

Most analyses reports show because of digitalization huge changes affecting up to hundreds of millions of jobs worldwide. According to the International Federation of Robotics (IFR) forecast, by 2022, nearly 4 million industrial robots may be present in various work processes, and this number might grow by up to 13% per year.

The fourth agricultural revolution is associated with game-changing technologies such as robotics, gene editing, and smart farming systems (Barrett and Rose, 2022). Digitalization increases the flow of information across the value chain, and digitalization technology has the potential to make crop production more efficient, environmentally friendly, and adapted to market changes (Birner et al., 2021)

Bode et al. (2018) use the automation probabilities estimated by Frey and Osborne (2017) to analyze the type of individuals who are more likely to be affected by automation of occupations. Using various household surveys for Germany, they show that individuals with certain socioeconomic and psychological characteristics are at a higher risk of digitalization, while characteristics typical of entrepreneurial individuals (e.g., higher levels of human capital, high openness to experiences, creativity) protect workers from automation of their jobs. It also appears that the occupational risk of automation is related to labor market transitions into self-employment and unemployment in Germany (Sorgner, 2017).

A recent study by Frey and Osborne (2017) that received substantial academic and media attention concludes that about 47 percent of the US labor forces are currently in jobs that are highly likely to be replaced by machines in the next one to two decades. This result has largely been confirmed by other studies for various countries, although the average risk of automation varied a lot across countries (see, e.g., Arntz et al. 2017, Sorgner et al. 2017).

Different surveys show that the 50% job opportunities are related to the information technology. In the OECD countries, 5% to 6% employment opportunities are based on the advance communication and technological processes (Borowiecki and Navarrete, 2017). Another study has presented that all industrial sectors i.e. primary, secondary and tertiary have become depended on technological systems. The organizations in these sectors have faced the major change in the attitude of employees. Especially, in tertiary and primary the employees have gained improvement in their daily activities. Due to this fact, the employees in these industries are willing to task risk or challenges. The more jobs have created in the industries, which has supported to improve the economic conditions of the world (Coreynen, Matthyssens and Van Bockhave, 2017).

The past literature has provided information about the increase in employment in the financial, hospitality, retail, marketing and service sectors. However, there is no research related to the employment ratio of manufacturing companies after the integration of digital systems and technologies. This is the major gap in the study of digitization process of different business sectors related to employment.

Therefore, it demands additional illustrations of the contribution of the different studies in the field of Digitalization and employment research domain. Most of the studies exist on specific framework used, their limitations and future research directions. Very few of the past studies done in the field of digitalization have considered the intellectual contributions, keywords used, most productive journals, annual average production co-occurrence of keywords, network mapping and so on (Hsiao et al., 2015; Johnson and Samakovlis, 2019). The current article is an attempt to fill the literature gap in a comprehensive manner through systematic literature review using bibliometric analysis technique to complement the existing review studies and provide a solid roadmap for the future research. Hence, the following three research questions have been formulated for conducting this study:

RQ1. What are the disclosed associations of Digitalization and Employment domain that can be evolved by using the bibliometric analysis?

RQ2. Who are the topped cited authors and research articles contributing to the effect of Digitalization on employment research?

RQ3. What are the main keywords discussed in the research work done in Digitalization and Employment?

RQ4. Which are the most influential documents, authors, sources, institutions, and countries in Digitalization (digital) and Employment research?

This paper aims to understand the acquaintance evolution and its present status, draw a thematic map, and identify future research directions. We achieve this by looking at the extant literature through an integrated lens of bibliometric analysis. The rest of the paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 explains the research methodology, followed by section 3 discusses the bibliometric analysis and findings, and section 4 offers discussion, future research directions, and a conclusion.

3. Research Methodology

Bibliometric analysis along with a citation and co-citation analysis presents a powerful way to analyze the patterns and characteristics of already published papers in scholarly field. It may also help to find out the school of thought, if any, in any specific area of study (Mandal, 2017; Christie, 2008). Citation and co-citation analysis focus on finding out the emergent themes in specific areas of study, the impact of different journals and different schools of thought (Nyagadza, 2020). Going beyond merely counting and collating citations, previous studies have pointed out the nature and course of development of a discipline to assess which journals and authors have created value to other researchers by collaboration. Bibliometric studies, such as citation and co-citation analyses, are useful for delving into the trends and characteristics of what has been written, making it easier to explore, organize, and articulate work done in a particular discipline (Diodato, 1994; Ferreira et al., 2014). Bibliometric analyses can help to guide collection growth, define institutional scholarship strengths and citation/co-citation trends, and identify possible schools of thought in a discipline (Lewis and Alpi, 2017). For a comprehensive investigation of written source documents (e.g., academic journal papers and books).

We have used systematic searching and filtering of data –

- 1) first, we have searched the database with certain search keywords,
- 2) then we refine the search criteria and considered appropriate studies and
- 3) then we analyzed the data. The data inclusion is based on the research articles only to emphasize over the authentic and published findings, subject area Business and Social Science.

From initial search from Scopus DB we got 70372 articles, the study used the 1992 to 2022 period in the search strategy and document selection process. While the number of documents from the early years is scanty, and the last decade has seen significant advancement in the field, the logic of using the more extended period is to avoid missing out on any seminal study. Data exclusion has been done further by eliminating studies which were not specific to the Digitalization and allied areas such as Automation, BI, IT, and Impacting value chain in Employment or job creation. The data has been first being extracted by using both search syntax and keywords in title of the research articles, and then all the data have been merged to convert into a single file. Search syntax for data collection includes (“Digitalization “OR “Automation) and (“Employment” or “Job”). The data extraction from the Scopus DB has been done in comma separated value (CSV) format for further processing as keywords for the search in author keywords, abstract, and title to find the articles related to Digitalization, IT, ICT, BI connected with digital technology. We restrict subject area to Business, Management, Accounting and Social Science. Therefore, ultimately 7586 articles were extracted for the current study.

Title, abstract, keyword, co-occurrence, Bibliometric coupling, citation analysis was performed using VOSviewer, which is based on VoS (visualization of similarities), as clustering methodology. Clusters so formed were identified using the VoS clustering technique. First, co-citation analysis was attempted to derive the structures of cited documents. This analysis epitomizes the citation strength by which the articles are cited with each other (Small, 1973; Marshakova, 1973) as the commonly cited documents tend to

form clusters of common research streams. Then we performed a co-occurrence analysis of keywords published in the author's keyword section of the research papers selected for this study. This analysis analyses the keywords that are frequently occurring in the selected articles (Su and Lee, 2010). We further used VOSviewer to form the research clusters and performed a content analysis of the key themes of research derived from these clusters.

4. Bibliometric Results and Discussion

General Trends of Publications

Figure:1 shows the growth the trend in the publication of the articles in the fields of Digitalization and Employment, it is evident from the figure that this field has drawn a significant surge in research interest is expanding and there exists an exponential growth after 2010, in 2011 the number of publications were 192 and in 10 years it reached in top 1468, but in between 1992-2005 the publications were almost static and numbers were between 65 to 100 in every year.

Figure 1: Documents by Year

Most influential contributions in terms of most cited sources, total citations and source impact

The quantity as well as quality of the contributions is taken into considered and analyzed on the basis of the citations, published documents and relative strengths of the papers. The total number of contributions in subject area is the general indicator of the attractiveness of the topics and sub-topics. The impact of each source is determined by the average citation per paper per year. The average citations per paper are being determined by calculating the average citation for a particular paper in a given year. The citation of a

source reflects that it has been referred by the scholars in their studies and been cited for being the most relevant paper in that area. Figure 2: shows that School of management and economics, Beijing tops the list of citation with 117 followed by montpellier business school, montpellier, France 77, Southampton business school, university of Southampton, Southampton, United Kingdom 63, department of management studies, Indian institute of technology Delhi, new Delhi, India 57 so on. In the VOS viewer output Figure 3, the size of the dot specifies the number of citations for a particular source.

Figure 2: Citation and Documents by Institutions

Figure 3: Citation by Institution

Figure 4 : Documents per year by sources

Categories and research areas

A list of the top categories is given in Figure 5: with Business management and Accounting contributed 44% of total publication followed by Engineering, Decision Sciences and Social Sciences contributed 14%, 11% and 9% respectively. The first three categories account for two-thirds of the total number of publications, indicating the advantages of management, business, Engineering and Decision Sciences research areas on the subject

Figure 5: Documents by Subject Area

Key contributing authors, affiliations and country

We have considered 22 scholars and their number of citations. The number of citations on an author's works signifies the quality of the research and relevance with the field of study. As represented in Figure 7, the authors who have maximum impact are bag s. dwivedi y.k., huang m.-h., gupta s, liu j. zhang x enjoying total with 1209 citations. Then rust r.t. with 152 and kumar v. with 147 citations while chen h. spot. Others authors are having their positions according to citations. The authors with more than 100 cited references have been organized in specific area of research who have used the similar references represented by the VOSviewer output

Figure 6: Authors, Documents citations and link strength

Figure 7: Citation Author

Top published countries, funding sponsors

From figure 8 and 9 : we can find that the literature mainly comes from developed countries such as USA, China and Europe. The data show that USA, UK, China, India has a significant influence in this area of research, followed by the Germany, Australia and Italy.

Figure 8: Documents by Country

Figure 9: Biographic Coupling relationship – country

Figure 7 list the top 11 institutions and funding agencies and provide detailed information on the geographical distribution of research institutions. National Natural Science Foundation of China plays an important role in this field which published almost 46% of total selected sponsors. Followed by National Science Foundation, Fundamental

Research Funds for the Central Universities and European Commission are the top sponsoring agencies respectively.

Figure 10: Publication by Funding Sponsors

Main keywords

For preparation of data, we used various keywords and refined them to get most appropriate studies for e-tourism. We found most appropriate 93 keywords which are being used for the keywords analysis (see Figure 11). VOSviewer output for keyword co-occurrence divides the total keywords into five clusters

Figure 11: Key Words Cluster Analysis

To explore the research domain and topics are clustered. Most occurred keywords are Digitalization falling in Cluster 1. In the network, five clusters are identified, highlighting the main cluster (red), which groups the largest number of terms linked to Digitalization and employment. The terms with the highest number of co-occurrences are: Commerce, Digital transformation, Digitalization, Employment. The second most important cluster 2 (green) includes keywords such as “AI”, “Big Data”, “ML” “SCM”, “Sustainability”, “Sustainable”, “Development”. “Technology Adoption”. Cluster 3 (Blue) includes keywords such as “Construction Industries”, “Project”, “Knowledge Management”, “Risk Management”, “Design”. Cluster 4 (Yellow) includes keywords such as “Automation”, “Digitalization “IoT”, “Manufacturing”, “Performance”, “Robotic Technology”, and the last cluster 5 (Purple) includes keywords such as “Economy and Social Effects”, “Energy Utilization”, “Industrial Research”, “Manufacturing”, “Production Control” and “Scheduling”.

Implications

Research implications

Results revealed that several branches of technological developments such as AI, IoT, SCM, ML, Automation have emerged into this research Domain. It provides a wider platform to the Digitalization and Its Impact researchers to evolve useful insights. The bibliometric review done for the time period 1992–2020 solicits a broader spectrum of understanding that may fill the research gap in the impact of Digitalization on Employment.

Managerial implications

Employers, Employee, Industry practitioners, Sponsors authorities, government and non-government bodies may get useful insights and find out the relationships of the Digitalization with the employment and make better policies and governance for the labor market.

Social implications

The upgradation in technology, changes in Business process and models are urging the adoption of IT in the labor market. The adoption of digitalization will uplift the social infrastructure with the proliferation of precise information that affect the employment. Society may access opportunities and information without involving much labor incentive human interaction and helps in maintain social distance.

5. Limitation and Future Research Direction

One of the major limitation of the study is that this research has considered only data from Scopus software and the analysis is based on software and algorithm and completely depends on the secondary data base which is indexed in Scopus. This analysis is data-driven and findings depend on the indexed publications, while searching there exist certain terms which are multidisciplinary or allied to area which results in studies that might not be much relevant and difficult to exclude completely. The data search for other related keywords such as digitalization, Automation employment and so on has not been

incorporated to avoid inclusion of some irrelevant literature. Future study may seek to incorporate these searches separately to develop a more intense spectrum for evaluating and finding the Real picture of the digitalization effect on employment. The area of digitalization offers lots of interesting avenues for further research in this field. As this area is relatively new and most of the aspects have not been studied much, and it can be expanded well in those prospective. The evolution of industry 4.0 technologies in the industry may be further studied. The scope and applications of digitalization may also be discussed in future. The challenges in Automation, ICT, AI, ML adoption in the industry as per the different geographical, economic and social aspects may also be an interesting area to be discussed.

6. Conclusion

Digitalization and Automation of manufacturing industries is becoming the apparatus of digital transformation of the economy. The aim of the current research is to enumerate and provide a comprehensive understanding existing research studied on the impact of Digitalization on employment by determining the published journals, the most prolific author, best university, countries in total contribution and the development and trends and to find out new areas for future research. By using VOSviewer software, a streamlined and lucid picture has been emerged. The analysis is providing a great visualization of the bibliographical information about the area of research. There is an increase in the number of publications in last 10 years, and it shows that the area is in its developing phase. Digitalization, SCM, robotic implementation, IoT, Automation, Sustainable Development, digital architecture, human-less interaction, ML and so on have emerged as the major trends in this research. The dynamic changes evolved in the nature of employment due to technological innovation soliciting a wider spectrum for the researcher.

The research carried out in this paper allows us to conclude that the scientific research related to digitalization and Employment is growing exponentially, and the main active countries are USA, UK Germany, U.S., and China. In addition, the scientific publications are developed collaboratively all over the world (Europe, America, and Asia-Pacific), the scientific powerhouses being the core or central part of the network. As far as organizations are concerned, School of management and economics, Beijing is the most productive organization; however, the articles by the montpellier business school, montpellier, France and Southampton business school, university of Southampton, Southampton, United Kingdom on scientific production. In terms of research topics, the network of one of the most influential universities allows us to define several main research fields relating to technologies: , digitalization, manufacturing, data analytics, process optimization, IoT, SM, among others. Therefore, it can be concluded that this is a very active field of research, opening the way to new investigations that make it possible to further the transfer of the knowledge generated (as co-citation analysis), in order to facilitate and promote new research to the scientific community.

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